

BIOBASED RESIN AS A MEANS TO TOUGHEN BIOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Biocomposites can be designed and engineered from natural/bio-fibers and unsaturated polyester resin/blend of polyester resin and derivitized vegetable oil to replace existing glass fiber-polyester composites for use in housing structures. Natural fiber composites (Biocomposites) would provide environmental gains, reduced energy consumption, lighter weight, insulation and sound absorption properties and would also eliminate health hazards unlike glass fiber composites thus providing many beneficial additions to the American Advanced Housing program. Biocomposites were made using a non-woven fiber mat (90% Hemp fiber with 10% thermoplastic polyester binder) as reinforcement, and unsaturated polyester (UPE) resin as well as blends of UPE and functionalized vegetable oils as the polymer matrix. All composites were made with 30 % volume fraction of fiber, which was optimized earlier . The structure-property relationships of this system as well as the thermo-mechanical properties of these composites were also measured using Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA), Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), and Thermo Gravimetric Analysis (TGA). The notched izod impact strength of biocomposites from biobased resin (blends of UPE and functionalized vegetable oil) and hemp fiber are enhanced by 90% as compared to that of the pure UPE- hemp fiber composites. The initial tests also show an improvement in the tensile properties of the composite as a result of the incorporation of the derivitized vegetable oil. Further experiments are aimed to study in detail the morphology of the composite using electron microscopy.

Keywords bioresin, biocomposite, natural fiber, vegetable oil

INTRODUCTION

Renewable materials from sustainable sources are becoming increasingly used in a variety of applications. Interest in the use of natural fibers has grown during the last decade due to their various advantages. Biocomposites, in general are materials made by nature or produced synthetically that include some type of natural material in their structure. In our research, biocomposites are also known as natural fiber composites. Biocomposites are formed through the combination of natural cellulose fibers with other resources such as biopolymers or resins or binders based on renewable raw materials. The objective is to combine two or more materials in such a way that a synergism between the components results in a new material that is much better than the individual components. The properties of plant fibers can also be modified through physical and chemical technologies to improve performance of the final biocomposite. Some of the plant fibers with suitable properties for making biocomposites are: hemp, kenaf, henequen, jute, flax, sisal, banana, kapok, etc. Biocomposites can be used for a range of applications, for example, building materials, structural and automotive parts, absorbents, adhesives and bonding agents and degradable polymers.

Vegetable oils such as soybean, cotton seed, linseed, castor, are available on a global basis in very large quantities at affordable costs. These naturally hydrophobic plant oils are used as starting materials for a

range of resin products currently under study at CMSC. Vegetable oils can be transformed to resin precursors that will polymerize when heated in the presence of catalysts. This technology uses reactivity of monomers to attack the double bonds present in the oil, forming linkages that can subsequently breakdown into crosslinkable units. Other reactive chemicals can be incorporated into the formulation to facilitate curing

In this study, bio-based resins were made by the addition of a derivitised vegetable oil to the unsaturated polyester resin matrix. This bio-resin was then used for the fabrication of a bio-composite using an optimum amount of natural fiber (30%volume). The natural fiber used was a non-woven hemp mat, which contains 10% polyethylene terephthalate (PET) as filler. The resulting composite was approximately 50% bio-based.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials. The polymer matrix used in this project is ortho unsaturated polyester resin (UPE), which was obtained from Kemlite Inc. The initiator used was methyl ethyl ketone peroxide (MEKP), and promoter used was cobalt naphthenate (CoNap). Both MEKP and CoNap were obtained from Aldrich. Pure, double refined, soybean oil was procured from Aldrich. Methyl ester of soybean oil (MESO) was kindly provided by AG Environmental Products. Epoxidized methyl linseedate (EML) was obtained from Atofina Chemicals. Non-woven hemp fiber mat containing 90% randomly oriented hemp fibers and 10% poly ethylene terephthalate (PET) as binder was kindly provided by FlaxCraft Inc. all materials were used as such without further purification.

Processing. The required amounts of fiber mats were vacuum dried for 5 hours. The polyester resin (UPE) was mixed well with MEKP and CoNap, in required amounts and then degassed under vacuum at room temperature for 5 minutes. The fiber mats were individually coated with the degassed resin. They were then placed between two aluminum plates covered with teflon release sheets. The plates were placed in a compression molding press (Carver® Laboratory Press) and the composites were cured at 80 psi for 2 hours at 100° C followed by 2 hours at 150° C. For making a control plaque from neat resin, degassed UPE solution was poured over degassed silicone molds and cured in a conventional oven using the same temperature profile. Soybean oil, EML and MESO were altered chemically by reaction with acrylonitrile monomer at elevated temperatures in the presence of a catalyst. Bioplastics were made by blending the UPE and the functionalized oils and curing them in silicone molds. Biocomposites were also made with hemp fiber mats and blends of UPE and functionalized oils as matrix by compression molding. The resulting plastic and composite plaques were cut into required shapes for various tests.

Analysis. The biocomposites, bioplastics and neat polyester samples were evaluated by flexural and notched Izod impact tests complying with ASTM D790 and ASTM D 256 standards respectively. The impact-fractured surfaces of plastics and composites were examined using Environmental Scanning Electron Microscopy (ESEM). DMA (TA DMA 2980) was performed to measure storage modulus, loss modulus and tan delta. For this test, rectangular sample bars were placed on the 3 point bending clamp in the furnace and heated at the rate of 4 °C per minute from room temperature to 150 °C.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Most unmodified thermosets are brittle materials at ambient temperature. In consequence, most polymers

Figure 1: *Impact Strength of bioplastics*

A= UPE control, B= MSO-UPE,
C= MEESO -PBMA-UPE, D= ESO-UPE

have to be impact modified in order to satisfy end-use requirements for rigid applications. In all cases, the problem can be solved by incorporating rubber domains into the polymer matrix. However, the nature and the size of the elastomeric phase has to be adapted to each polymer matrix. In most cases, it is also desirable to use the minimum amount of rubber modifier, in order not to affect other physical properties such as modulus. The most important characteristics of an impact modifier are: rubber glass transition temperature, rubber domain particle size in the matrix, quality of dispersion, adhesion to the polymer matrix. Historically several technical approaches for toughening have been developed, which can be divided into three categories all based on the incorporation of an elastomeric damping phase: elastomer introduction during polymerization, dispersion of a thermoplastic elastomer phase during compounding (uncrosslinked), and incorporation of elastomeric core-shell particles

Figure 2: *Flexural properties of bioplastics*

A= UPE control, B= MSO-UPE,
C= MEESO -PBMA-UPE, D= ESO-UPE

Impact energy is the energy absorbed into the specimen during the impact event divided by its cross-sectional area. For the bioplastics, the impact strength increased after addition of bio-based oil into the matrix (Figure 1). The impact strength of plastic containing MESO is 25% higher than that of neat UPE resin, and impact strength of plastic containing EML is 96% higher than neat UPE resin. But the trend in flexural properties is opposite to that of impact strength. All bioplastics have lower bending strength and elastic modulus as compared to neat UPE resin (Figure 2). The bending strength of plastic containing modified MESO is 20% lower than strength of neat resin, and its modulus is 30% lower than that of neat resin. In the case of biocomposites made with blends of oils and resin, the impact strength increases, but the flexural properties decrease. The impact strength of biocomposite containing hemp fibers in a matrix of bioresin, is 96% more than that of biocomposite made with hemp fibers and UPE resin (Figure 3). However, the bending strength of the biocomposite with bioresin is 20% lower than that of biocomposite with neat resin and the modulus of elasticity for this biocomposite is 30% lower than that of biocomposite with neat UPE resin (Figure 4).

Figure 3: Impact strength of biocomposites
 A=UPE plastic, B=untreated hemp-UPE,
 C=UPE-EML plastic, D= untreated hemp-UPE-EML

of their molecular structure, and when they are added to the polyester matrix, they lower the stiffness of the resulting material. The glass transition temperature of neat UPE resin, obtained from tan delta plot is 95°C (figure not shown). For all bioplastics, the T_g decreases by 10-12°C as compared to neat UPE resin. The glass transition temperatures of plastics based on vegetable oils have been reported from 40 to 80°C in the literature [3,4].

Figure 4: Flexural properties of biocomposites
 A=UPE plastic, B=untreated hemp-UPE,
 C=UPE-EML plastic, D= untreated hemp-UPE-EML

the rubber phase. Depending on the polymer system, either a single mechanism or a combination of different mechanisms will be activated.

ESEM micrographs of the impact fractured surfaces of the bioplastics show phase separation (Figures 5 and 6). These pictures show discrete microstructures of the dispersed phase which are scattered throughout the entire surface.

Following the trend of flexural properties, the storage modulus for bioplastics decreases in the same manner as compared to the neat resin. As seen with bending strength and modulus of elasticity, there is a 20-30% reduction in the storage modulus of the bioplastic (figure not shown). This result was expected because vegetable oils are intrinsically low modulus materials because

Traditionally, elastomer additives have been used for toughening in the free radical cross-linking of unsaturated polyester resin [1]. But polyester blends with vegetable based oils can also achieve the same purpose. The blends of oils and polyester resin form semi immiscible systems. Here, the oil phase provides the rubbery structures after curing. Polymers are often reinforced by the introduction of a rubbery phase, so-called impact modifier, in order to absorb impact energy and to avoid or delay catastrophic failure.

The main toughening mechanisms which have been identified are namely: crazing of the polymer matrix, shear yielding of this matrix, and cavitation of

A small amount of discrete rubbery particles, with an average size of a few microns which are randomly distributed in a glassy brittle polyester thermoset, dissipate part of the impact energy, and thus improve crack and impact resistance without a major decrease in other properties of unmodified resin thermoset. The main role of the rubber phase in toughened resins is to relieve the constraints in the matrix through principal mechanisms of capitation and forming shear bands [2].

Figure 5: ESEM micrographs of impact fractures surface of bioplastic containing altered MSO-PBMA-UPE, a) Magnification 2000X, Scale 25 μm , b) 250 X, Scale 200 μm

The miscibility and interfacial properties of additive and resin blends play a major role in the toughening process. Improvements in the fracture impact of thermoset polyester resin can be obtained by dispersing elastomer particles with diameters from 0.5 to 5 microns in the blends. The smaller particles produce more microcracks in the matrix and enhance the fracture–impact energy. The additive is immiscible with the resin and gets phase separated from the matrix during curing. This phase separation phenomenon is similar to that in low profile mechanism of unsaturated polyester resins.

Unsaturated polyester resins systems are very reactive materials, which are initially in a liquid state, and become solid after curing. Thermodynamics and polymerization kinetics are the deciding factor for the morphology of the system.

Phase separation brings about a change in polydispersity. Usually, the size of additive particles in the matrix is 1-40 microns. A way to reduce this size is to decrease interfacial tension between two phases. Adding a small percentage of coupling agent like maleic anhydride solves this problem.

Therefore, smaller microcracks were formed in the matrix leading to an increase in impact strength. These microcracks are produced during the large volumetric shrinkage which takes place during polymerization. Microvoids also occur around the fillers and fibers in the composite.

Microvoid formation is an important phenomenon for systems consisting of blends of bioresin and UPE. It compensates for resin shrinkage, but induces intrinsic brittleness. Increased additive content in the UP resin should produce higher impact strength, but if the microvoid content is also enhanced, impact strength is reduced.

Well-dispersed particles in the resin matrix induce homogeneous distribution of internal stresses due to network formation. Thus, low energy impact breaks in the unsaturated polyester resin composites can be omitted by the use of this additive into the system.

Figure 6: ESEM micrographs of impact fractures surface of bioplastic containing altered MSO-UPE, a) Magnification 300 X, Scale 150 μm b) Magnification 2000X, Scale 25 μm

CONCLUSIONS

Using bioresins as polymer matrices provides a two fold edge over thermoset resins in biocomposites. Their presence can improve the impact strength of the resulting bioplastic, as well as produce a material with higher biobased content. Further experiments are aimed to study in detail the behavior of second phase, actual mechanism of toughening and control of dispersed phase. Also, the structure -property relationships are to be determined. It is also planned to study the fractured surfaces to find the critical parameters like fiber-matrix adhesion and fracture dynamics.

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